

10 kg H₂/day Pilot plant

Design of modular pilot plant for ammonia cracking

ABSTRACT

The SINGLE project revolves around ammonia cracking using Proton Ceramic Electrochemical Membrane Reactor (PCER) to produce green hydrogen, enabling the process to be done in one step within this equipment. To validate the technology, a pilot plant has been designed and built to test it in an industry-like environment during prolonged periods of time. To implement these reactors in the Balance of Plant (BoP) of the pilot, a purpose-built module has been designed for integration, stacking 20 units of PCERs to enable a production of 10 kg/day of Hydrogen. The plant has been built in GECRIO (Balaguer, Spain), and it's operated near Valencia, Spain, in the PTI Transfer facilities.

Key points

- Stack module design and manufacturing: PCER integration in high temperature and corrosive environments
- Pilot plant design: Design and assembly of 10 kg/day ammonia cracking plant

Related KERs or Info-packs

- KER 2: PCER module design
- KER 3: 10 kg H₂/day pilot

Introduction

To face the challenge of hydrogen transportation, the SINGLE project aims to develop and test an ammonia cracking solution that enables on-site hydrogen production in small to medium scales. In these production levels, the current state of the art doesn't allow the use of ammonia as a transport vector, so a compact and energy effective solution is developed in the SINGLE project to meet these demands.

To test the developed technology, a pilot plant has been designed and assembled to prove and validate the previously mentioned statements, with the aim of operating the PCER reactors in what will be industry-like production cycles, aiming for test runs of 500 hours. This will enable stress testing and efficiency validation of multiple stacks simultaneously, giving great insight in PCER ammonia cracking operation and maintenance, and preparing the technology for scale up operations with industrial scale units.

Stack module design and manufacturing: PCER integration in high temperature and corrosive environments

At the heart of SINGLE is a modular unit ("the module") designed with integrated manifolds for gas distribution, thermal management, and electrical connections. This module hosts several membrane stack reactors, each enclosed in a dedicated steel vessel and maintained in a controlled thermal environment. It is designed to be easily integrated with other modules in diverse BoP configurations.

One of the central engineering challenges addressed in the project was the management of high-temperature ammonia. Limited prior research existed on the behaviour of concentrated ammonia at elevated temperatures regarding its interaction with structural steels. Since the stack vessels and connections must endure high temperatures, pressures, and the corrosive effects of ammonia (nitridation) over extended operating periods, dedicated research was conducted within SINGLE to identify and validate the most suitable steel alloys, ensuring extended durability of critical components.

A parallel design effort focused on operational optimization of the module combines electrochemical modelling with CFD simulations. This software platform enables the optimization of gas flow patterns and minimizes temperature gradients both within and across the stacks, under endothermic, thermoneutral, or exothermic operation modes. In the longer term, this flexibility will allow the same stack technology to be deployed in various integration scenarios, depending on the availability and demand for heat. Multiple thermocouples and sensors are embedded throughout the system, monitoring the response of individual stack vessels as well as the overall environment within the module. This monitoring capability forms the basis for improved control strategies and reliable long-term operation.

Pilot plant design: Design and assembly of 10 kg/day ammonia cracking plant

Design

Through close collaboration between the PCER manufacturer and the SINGLE project's materials and chemical specialists, a 10 kg/day production module was designed to ensure safe and reliable operation.

Figure 1: Pilot envelope

The pilot plant has been implemented within a 25 ft custom container, enabling easy transport and installation. The envelope includes three distinct rooms, a water purification and refrigeration station, a control room, and the main process zone where the PCER module and BoP is located.

The BoP consists of an initial stage of fluid regulation, where the desired mass flow mix is created for the two channels that feed the PCER stacks. This mix will depend on the operation protocol that's desired by the plant operator, ranging between start-up, shut-down, normal production, etc. Once the mix is obtained, it will be heated to the desired temperature and fed to the stacks to enable the ammonia cracking reaction. The module itself will heat the feed products further to reach the desired cracking temperature, extracting the hydrogen from the nitrogen stream in the process. Finally, the reaction products are cooled and water is separated, leaving dry hydrogen as a product.

To enable an efficient ammonia conversion rate, temperatures higher than 700 °C must be reached, which has posed a problem with material compatibility, mainly due to high corrosion produced by high temperature ammonia. To enable the BoP to function, material analysis and testing was performed to select the correct alloy for each step of the process, derisking the design process and contributing to the operational safety of the plant.

Ammonia is a highly toxic gas, so a set of design standards and safety equipment has been implemented to ensure that the pilot plant can function safely, without posing a threat to the operators and maintenance technicians. This includes a gas warning system, that operates within the PLC of the plant, an ammonia disposal system, that eliminates ammonia ejections outside the plant, and finally a set of PPIs for the personnel.

Assembly and equipment fabrication

The pilot plant is housed within a steel container, with three distinct rooms. Firstly, in the purification and refrigeration room, a set of ion cartridge filtration steps have been implemented to purify the input water, which is then pumped to the main BoP room. This room also contains the refrigeration system of the plant, which is centred around a mini chiller unit, with a regulation panel for the different refrigeration streams.

The control room is situated in the middle of the container. It contains the power and control cabinets as well as a rack for power sources. It includes a climatization system and a chair and table for the plant operator, who will be able to control the plants SCADA from a computer at the mounted desk.

Finally, we have the BoP room, which is the bigger of the three. The room layout follows the process of the plant. First, we have a panel with mass flow controllers that define the flow and composition

of the mix fed to the reactors. After that, the mix is heated to the desired temperature by a set of evaporators and heaters, which is finally divided into different streams and fed to the reactor. Once the reaction is completed, the products are cooled, and water is extracted to leave streams of pure hydrogen and nitrogen. After

Figure 2: Control room

the reaction has occurred, samples are extracted from each channel, and they are sent to the same panel as the reaction products, where they go through the same process of water separation. Once the sample is treated, it is sent to the chromatograph, where the operator selects between the different sample points with the aid of a set of selector valves.

Conclusions

Pilot plants represent a crucial step in the development of the PCER technology, enabling the validation of stacks in assemblies that resemble industrial deployment. The pilot plant designed will help to improve future designs, operation and safety protocols and maintenance procedures. For the technology to improve and climb the TRL ladder, future plants, with higher capacities and constructed and operating in industrial environments will be necessary, but the know how produced in SINGLE will aid in de-risking these next steps.

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